

The Book of Judith

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The Book of Judith is an ancient Jewish work which details the resistance of Judith, a pious widow, who assassinates an Assyrian general besieging her town. The work narrates the attempted invasion of Judea by Holofernes, and the heroism of Judith, who prevents the destruction of the people and the Jerusalem Temple through her faithfulness, but also her cunning and leadership. The work is often described as being of two halves; the first seven chapters cover the conquests of the Assyrian army and introduce the character of Achior, while chapters eight to sixteen narrate Judith's infiltration of the Assyrian camp, successfully assassinating Holofernes and breaking the siege of her hometown Bethulia. The work is commonly part of the Christian canon, although at least since Jerome, it was not considered on a par with the core of the Hebrew Bible and was attributed a so-called "deuterocanonical" status. The work appears to have limited impact amongst early Jewish readers; there are some references to Judith in rabbinic sources, mostly clustered around particular associations between Judith and Hannukah. The work was likely composed around the beginning of the 1st century BCE, although there is some debate about the exact circumstances which may have led to the composition. The earliest reference to the work is known from Clement of Rome, writing around the end of the 1st century CE. The manuscript evidence begins in the 3rd century CE with seven verses of chapter fifteen inscribed on a pot sherd, and the major codices of the 4th and 5th centuries (Sinaiticus, Vaticanus and Alexandrinus) have the full text, with some differences. These earliest textual witnesses are all in Greek. It was thought for a long time (and presented by Jerome) that the work was likely originally composed in Hebrew, but more recent work has begun to argue strongly in favour of a Greek original; Hebrew features of the text can be explained through connections with the Greek of the Septuagint (the Greek translations of the Hebrew Bible). The work has inspired a lot of artist representation, which has furthered interest in the Book of Judith, but has also on occasion tended to misrepresent the evidence of the work itself. One notable case is the famous Caravaggio painting of Judith Beheading Holofernes (1598-1599), where Judith's maid (or slave) is depicted as an old woman. This woman is said to outlive Judith, herself dying aged 105. While not a significant mistake, the artistic tradition nevertheless contributes to ongoing reception of the Book of Judith.

Date Range: 160 BCE - 80 CE

Region: Levant

Region tags: Middle East, Israel

Levant

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gera, Deborah Levine. *Judith*. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2014.
- Source 2: Zenger, Erich. *Das Buch Judit*. Edited by Werner Georg Kummel. Gütersloher Verlagshaus, 2019.
- Source 3: Wills, Lawrence M. *Judith*. Edited by Sidnie White Crawford. Minneapolis, MN: Fortress, 2019.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.codexsinaiticus.org/en/>
- Source 1 Description: Codex Sinaiticus, one of the earliest witnesses to the text of the Book of Judith

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://jwa.org/encyclopedia/article/judith-apocrypha>
- Source 1 Description: Encyclopaedia entry by Toni Craven

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Other textile: Parchment

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Other [specify]: Possible translation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: Later manuscripts were illuminated but the earliest evidence has no accompanying imagery

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Notes: It is uncertain where such texts were stored in antiquity, but this is a possibility

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It has been suggested that the text was used to bolster the reputation of Queen Shalamzion (Alexandra Salome) and perhaps was associated with the court, but this is debated - see Tal Ilan's work here.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is difficult to say. The text was used within the Catholic tradition and perhaps interpretation was regulated.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any specific gender designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any age designation?

– No

↳ Is the select group of people defined by any form of linguistic designation?

– Yes

Notes: Would generally be called scribes.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: The question of the language of the Book of Judith has been the subject of debate. It has long been recognised that the oldest preserved text in Greek shows a large degree of influence from Hebrew written conventions. The debate has largely come to recognise that this Greek is heavily influenced by Greek translations of the Hebrew Bible, and as such, reflects a kind of

distinctive language, influenced by a set of texts considered to be significant.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– No

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– No

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– I don't know

Notes: Yes in the reception history, not as such in the original writing of the text

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

↳ Calligraphy?

– I don't know

Notes: There may be some calligraphy in some of the manuscript tradition, but I am not aware of any,

↳ Illustrations?

– I don't know

Notes: As part of the long reception history of Judith, there have been many artistic representations of parts of the narrative.

↳ Illuminations?

– I don't know

Notes: There are likely many illuminated manuscripts of the Book of Judith available, but these are also part of the much later tradition accompanying the transmitted text of Judith.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: There are ancient versions of Judith in Greek, Latin and Syriac (although this is likely dependent on the Latin) and there are also multiple recensions of the Greek Judith. The tradition is rich in variation and determinations on priority are difficult to establish.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Notes: The Greek is generally viewed to be the oldest extant version, and the small variations are not significant in terms of the overall narrative.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– I don't know

Notes: The text was included in large collections of works, but eventually became part of the Apocrypha.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: At one stage certainly, now perhaps not.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

Notes: In antiquity this appears to have been the case. Jerome had a sense that the work was part of the so-called Deuterocanonical works, but nevertheless was significant.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Apocryphal

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: Rituals of fasting, festival observance, temple dedication, prayer, and bathing are all attested to in the text.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– No

Notes: Members of Judith's genealogy are significant insofar as they may represent various types of authority in Second Temple Judaism, but this chain ends with Judith. It does not continue beyond her.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: Elements of legal codes are present in the subtext, but there is not clear expression of exactly what should be done in a specific setting as in a formal legal code. The work is wholly narrative or takes the form of poetry.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Luni-solar? (Combined, as in Mayan, Javanese, or Cham calendars)

Notes: There are references to Sabbath observances, and certain festivals, but these are not clearly explained in the text itself; it relies on other knowledge.

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

Notes: There are harvests referenced in Judith 4:5; 8:2 but it is not regulated here.

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Perhaps the date of Nebuchadnezzar's invasion is significant (eighteenth year, 22nd day of the first month), Judith 2:1.

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

Notes: This is not proscriptive, but Judith mourns for a symbolic 40 months after the death of her husband, Judith 8:4.

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

–Specify: Passing mention in Judith 8:6

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

–All members

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

–number: Unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

Notes: This seems to be implied in Judith 16:18-20.

- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?
 - No

- ↳ Pilgrimages?
 - No

- ↳ Feasting?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed in accordance with the guidelines of the text?
 - Yes

Notes: The text does not establish guidelines themselves, but merely notes that Judith properly observes fasts, lunar events and festival days.

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that produced the text/copies of the text?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific locations in accordance with guidelines from the text?
 - Yes

- ↳ Specify

–Specify: A banquet is held by the elders of the town (Judith 6:21) although it is unclear if this is a festival banquet.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: This notion is perhaps alluded to in Judith 8:14, but this is unclear.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Manasseh is buried "with his ancestors in the field between Dothan and Balamon." (Judith 8:3).
Judith is also buried here in what is described as a cave (Judith 16:23).

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Judith mourns for 40 months, wearing sackcloth and widow's clothing, within a tent on her roof, and fasting (Judith 8:4-6).

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The only place where the deity is active in the narrative is in Judith 4:13 - here hearing prayers.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

Notes: However, Judith does say that the deity is not like a mere mortal, Judith 8:16.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Notes: There is a priestly class, and Judith also praises certain individuals with

connections to the deity. See Judith 8:26-27. Judith herself is also an elite and may have some kind of special connection.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– I don't know

Notes: This seems probable given the praise, but not explicit in the text.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Notes: This is largely unclear in the narrative, but implied.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: See the descriptions of what Judith accomplishes in Judith 13:15; 16:5 etc., although compare with the praise of Judith in Judith 15:10.

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

Notes: Within the narrative framework, this is unclear, although there is a lot of language around the directing of divine will over characters and the situation.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: The texts portrays communication with the divine but does not clearly function as a means by which to communicate with the deity, although this is perhaps possible.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– I don't know

Notes: Judith references the sons of Titans and tall giants in her song, but these are unclear, Judith 16:6.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: Nebuchadnezzar sets himself up as a god (via Holofernes), Judith 3:8.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: There are allusions to this kind of practice without an specifications in Judith 5:5-21; 6:2; 10:13; 11:5-19.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– No

↳ Food?

– Yes

Notes: Burnt offerings (Judith 16:18)

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Burnt offerings (Judith 16:18)

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

Notes: It could be considered that the killing of Holofernes is constructed akin to human sacrifice, but this would be highly unusual in the tradition of Second Temple Judaism, where human sacrifice is entirely prohibited.

↳ Sacred objects?

– Yes

Notes: Certain offerings (Judith 16:18)

↳ Daily life objects?

– Yes

Notes: Sackcloth as a sign of mourning around the altar (Judith 4:12).

↳ Other?

– Specify: War booty

Notes: Possessions of Holofernes are offered to the temple, along with his canopy ((Judith 16:19)

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

Notes: However, the narrative is clear in presenting Judith as a counter-part to Jael, who herself only kills Sisera after having sex with him (seemingly implied in Judges 4); Judith kills Holofernes without sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

Notes: Judith herself frequently presents half-truths to the Assyrians.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– No

Notes: Judith herself could be said to disrespect the elders of Bethulia, Judith 8:11-27.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– I don't know

Notes: This does not seem to be explicit in the text but likely assumed.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– I don't know

Notes: This does not seem to be explicit in the text but likely assumed.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– I don't know

Notes: However, there is an interesting passage where Achior undergoes conversion. There is no divine commentary on this. See Judith 14:6-10.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

Notes: Purification undertaken prior to entering the temple, Judith 16:18.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

Notes: This seems to be implied in Judith 16:2-5.

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Assyrian divine pretensions and attack on the deity's people are punished through complete annihilation, Judith 15:1-6.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– No

↳ Consists of bad luck?

– No

↳ Political failure?

– No

↳ Defeat in battle?

– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?

– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?

– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?

– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: This seems to be implied.

↳ Highly emphasized?

– No

- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - No
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Judith lives to the age of 105, Judith 16:23.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

- No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Judith observes a mourning fast and perhaps continues this in the Assyrian camp, only eating at night, Judith 8:6; 12:9.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: War booty in Judith 16:19.

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Notes: Perhaps this is assumed in Judith putting herself at risk, but no where mandated.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Notes: Judith observes certain festivals, and ritually washes, but this is not mandated anywhere, merely assumed.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: This seems to be implied in Judith 15:14; 16:18.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– Yes

Notes: Achior is circumcised to become part of the people, Judith 14:10.

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

Notes: Judith seems to allude to some such taboos, but unclear (Judith 12:1-2).

↳ Hair?

– No

↳ Dress?

– Yes

Notes: Judith observes widowhood dress, and also dresses herself in such a way so as to accomplish her goal.

↳ Ornaments?

– Yes

Notes: Judith puts on certain items, including a tiara, anklets, bracelets, rings, earrings and other jewellery (Judith 10:3-4).

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Notes: Judith refers to those in Bethulia and Judea as "brothers" (Judith 8:22, 24).

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

Notes: Burnt offerings, freewill offerings and gifts (Judith 16:18).

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– No

Notes: Not explicitly within this text but likely reliant on other traditions, see Judith 16:18-19.

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– Yes

Notes: War booty including Holofernes' canopy, Judith 16:19.

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– No

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: Burnt offerings.

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: War booty

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– I don't know

Notes: The celebration of the Assyrian defeat is commemorated by "all Israel." (Judith 15:14; 16:18)

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Judaism, perhaps Hasmonean or Herodian kingdoms/priestly temple-states

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Notes: The work was preserved in Christian communities and largely lost in Jewish tradition. The work itself was re-translated into Hebrew in the middle ages, but this was likely dependent on the Latin textual tradition.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– Yes

↳ Does the text advocate for public food storage?

– No

↳ Does the text provide guidance for food distribution?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate places for civic functions?

– No

Notes: Some kind of public place seems to be where decisions are made, but also at Judith's house in Judith 8:9-11.

↳ Does the text regulate places for the practice of justice?

– No

Notes: Some kind of public place seems to be where decisions are made, but also at Judith's house in Judith 8:9-11.

↳ Does the text advocate or specify controls for water management (irrigation, flood control)?

– Yes

Notes: Bethulia is supplied by spring water, which can be seized by the Assyrians, Judith 7:13, 17.

- ↳ Does the text specify restrictions on common transportation?
 - No

Taxation

- Does the text specify forms of taxation?
 - No

Warfare

- Does the text mention warfare?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?
 - No

- ↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?
 - Yes
 - Notes: A foreign commander (Achior) is incorporated into the people, but he does not have a military role beyond this point.

- ↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
 - Yes
 - Notes: It also celebrates successful resistance to this exogenous military force.

Food Production

- Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?
 - Yes

- ↳ Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?
 - Yes

- ↳ Characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]
 - Other [specify]: Judith 8:3, 7 refers to the fields and livestock of Manasseh and Judith.

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

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